

EFFECT OF TRM ON THE FLEXURAL PERFORMANCE OF RC BEAMS

S. Rakhshani, A. Rteil*, M. Komeili, A. S. Milani

School of Engineering, University of British Columbia, Kelowna, Canada

* Corresponding author ahmad.rteil@ubc.ca)

Keywords: *Textile reinforced mortar, Flexural behavior, Strengthening of concrete structures, Serviceability, Load carrying capacity*

1 General introduction

Plain concrete is a brittle material with a very low tensile strength which results in cracking under the service load. The crack can allow water and chemical agents to go through the concrete and cause damage to the concrete and steel reinforcement. Repairing damaged concrete structures is an economical way to extend the working life of a structure [1]. In addition, increasing the load carrying capacity could be required due to change of use of structure or to make it conform with new design standards and requirements [2].

Concrete structures of insufficient shear and flexural capacities are often strengthened by various methods such as shotcrete, applying different types of concrete overlays, adding post-tensioned cables, bonding steel plates or using composite materials. Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) materials have been successfully applied to strengthen existing reinforced concrete (RC) structures over the past two decades. FRP has several advantages including excellent corrosion resistance, high stiffness and strength-to-weight ratios, low thermal expansion, good fatigue performance, non-magnetic properties, easy to transport and tailor-ability. However, FRPs have drawbacks as well specially related to the use of polymer resin that can occasionally limit their use. These include a poor thermal behaviour above the polymer resin glass transition temperature, destruction during fire [3], non-applicability on wet surfaces or at low temperatures [4] and the incompatibility of polymer resin and concrete substrate [5]. As an alternative, textile composite materials bonded with cement based adhesive such as textile reinforced mortar/concrete (TRM/TRC) have been designed and developed more recently for both strengthening and rehabilitation of concrete structures [6, 7].

It is known that textile reinforced mortar/concrete (TRM/TRC) materials are more compatible with the concrete substrate materials and can provide a substantial gain in compressive strength and deformability of structures [7], crack resistance [8], and better performance at high temperatures and during fires [9] while maintaining other FRP advantages.

The TRM's mortar should meet some requirements in order to be a high quality matrix and applicable. These requirements are: non-shrinkable; high workability (easy to apply using a trowel); high viscosity (can be applied on vertical or overhead surfaces); low rate of workability loss (application of each mortar layer should be possible while the previous one is still in a fresh state); and sufficient shear (hence tensile) strength, in order to avoid premature de-bonding [7].

In textile reinforced mortar (TRM), the fibres are formed into the shape of multi-axial woven fabric textiles and combine with a matrix of fine grained cementitious mortar. A sample of TRM is shown in Figures 1 and 2 [10].

The mechanical properties of the textile and the mortar influence the performance of the TRM reinforced RC beams [11]. The quasi-ductile behaviour after matrix cracking is one the biggest advantage of TRM and it is very important for applications in civil engineering. This is due to the crack bridging of the textile and the de-bonding of the textile and cementitious matrix. The reinforcement structure leads to a crack pattern with small crack openings in conjunction with small crack spacing. This leads to the major influence of the post cracking behaviour of concrete on the overall response of the structural member [11]. In addition, with aligning fibres in the direction of tensile stresses of an RC beam, higher load carrying capacity and serviceability will be achieved [12].

Recent experimental and theoretical work showed the effectiveness of cement-base composites for strengthening of reinforced concrete structures. Examples include TRM jacketing as a solution for confinement of RC columns [13] for non-seismic and seismic purposes [15], for controlling the buckling of near surface mounted FRP (NSM FRP) [14], in the case of column confinement and column jacketing, and for strengthening RC-members or masonry walls [16].

2 Objective of this study

In this study, the effect of using different types of textile composites on the ensuing flexural performance of RC beams is examined by means of finite element modeling (FEM).

Three different types of textile materials for strengthening the RC beam were evaluated, namely carbon fabric, steel fabric and polyphenylene benzobisoxazole (PBO) fabric.

3 Case study

3.1 Problem description

The performance of TRM strengthened beams was evaluated numerically using a two-dimensional finite element (FE) model in Abaqus/Standard. In order to be able to validate the FE results, the model was adapted from an experimental study reported in the literature [3]. The length, width and depth of the RC beam were considered, respectively, to be 2200 mm, 400 mm, and 250 mm. The concrete beam was reinforced with three steel rebars (Figure 3) and was loaded in four-point bending with a clear span of 2200 mm, and loading points were at 750 mm from each end of the beam. The total load was applied step by step up to failure of the beam in a displacement control manner. Failure was defined as when (1) concrete reaches the compressive strain of 0.0035 (i.e., concrete crushing), (2) the steel reaches the yielding strain of 0.002 and (3) TRM reaches its tensile fracture strain.

The beam was modeled in Abaqus as 1/3 two-dimensional model due to the symmetry conditions. The beam was modeled without and with three different types of TRM reinforcements. Figures 4 and 5 show samples of the distribution of the plastic strain in unstrengthened and TRM reinforced RC beam at the failure point.

The following assumptions were made for the model: (1) a linear strain distribution through the full depth of the cross-section of the beam; (2) no tensile strength in concrete; (3) no slip between the concrete

and the steel rebars, (4) no slip or de-bonding between the concrete and the composite.

3.2 Material properties

Mechanical properties of concrete and steel used in the model were similar to those reported by Ambrisi and Focacci [3].

3.2.1 Concrete

The concrete has an elastic modulus of 30 GPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.2, the compression strength of 47.68 MPa, and a maximum compression strain of 0.0035 (Table 1).

3.2.2 Steel reinforcement (rebar)

The steel rebar was assumed having an elastic, perfectly plastic behaviour with identical moduli in tension and compression. The steel rebar was treated as a uni-axial material throughout the beam section and defined as a one-dimensional element embedded in the concrete. The rebar and the concrete failure behaviour were considered independently. The steel rebars has a yield stress of 523 MPa, a modulus of elasticity of 200 GPa and a size of 14 mm in diameter (Table 1).

3.2.3 Textile reinforced mortar

The performance of the following textile reinforcing materials was compared:

1. A balanced net of steel fibers with fibres along two orthogonal directions.
2. A balanced net of carbon fibres with fibres along two orthogonal directions.
3. A balanced net of poly(p-phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole) or PBO fibres with fibres along two orthogonal directions.

The mechanical properties of the three fibres are shown in Table 2. The cementitious matrix properties were similar to concrete properties shown in Table 1.

It should be noted that once a crack is formed in the concrete or the mortar matrix the tensile force is transferred through the rebar or the textile reinforcement. Therefore, "tension stiffening" was introduced into the concrete cracking model (Figure 6).

3.3 Validation of the FE model

The load-deflection behaviour from the base FE model (with no TRM reinforcement) was first verified by comparing it to the theoretical values calculated using the Canadian design code (CSA

A23.3-04) and to previous experimental data [3]. The results are presented in Figure 7.

3.3.1 Theoretical validation

The properties of the concrete and the steel rebars that were used in the analytical validation are those in Tables 1 and 2. Three points on the load-deflection curve were calculated, namely concrete cracking, steel yield and beam failure. Results of the theoretical analysis showed that the first crack point happened at the displacement of 0.91 mm and a load of 38.36 kN. The steel yielded at a displacement of 9.39 mm and a load of 136.84 kN. Failure, defined as concrete crushing after steel yielding, occurred at a displacement of 27.71 mm and a load of 142.91 kN. These results are reported in Table 3 and are shown in Figure 7.

3.3.2 Experimental validation

Figure 7 presents a comparison between the load-displacement curve plots for the un-strengthened beam from the experimental study [3] and the current FE model. A good agreement between the FE model and experimental data is seen.

The small difference between the experiment and the FE model could be caused by one of the following reasons: (1) due to the complex nature of the concrete it is always difficult to produce a concrete with uniform mechanical properties along the length of the beam; (2) micro-cracks are present in the experimental beams prior to loading and could be produced by drying shrinkage in the concrete and/or handling of the beams. The present FE model does not account for these micro-cracks that may reduce the stiffness of the experimental beams; and (3) in the FE model, a perfect bonding between concrete and rebar was assumed. In experimental cases, local breaking of bond is unavoidable and bond-slip takes place.

4 Parametric study on the effect of TRM

In order to study the effect of TRM and the type of textile used, multiple FE models were run and compared. Except for adding TRM to the soffit of the beam, the models were the same as the validated model described in Section 3 (Figure 8).

4.1 Effect of TRM on load-carrying capacity

Results from the FE model with different TRM systems is shown in Figure 8. In general, adding TRM sheets improved the flexural behaviour of the TRM strengthened RC beams compared to the control (unstrengthened beam). The effect of

strengthening depends on the TRM's elastic modulus. The load carrying capacity was increased by 135.60% for PBO TRM, 131.62% for Carbon TRM and 66.37% for Steel TRM by using a 1 cm thick TRM compared to the control beam. Similarly, the yield load of the strengthened beams increased by adding TRM systems. The increase was 58.29%, 54.12% and 36.26% for the PBO, steel and carbon TRM systems, respectively, compared to the control beam.

Figure 9 shows the variation of the normalized load with the modulus of elasticity of the different TRM systems. There is an asymptotic limit as to how much the elastic modulus of the TRM system can influence the improvement of the flexural behaviour and increasing the load capacity of the RC beam.

4.2 Effect of TRM on serviceability

Figure 10 shows the effect of adding TRM sheets on the midpoint deflection. A decrease in the midpoint deflection was observed as the elastic modulus of the TRM system was increased. The midpoint deflection was decreased by 62.45% for PBO TRM, 58.23% for carbon TRM and 43.04% for steel TRM when using a 1 cm thick TRM compared to the control beam. This decrease can lead to better serviceability of the reinforced concrete beam and concrete structures in general.

4.3 Effect of TRM on general load-deflection curve

All of the modeled strengthened beams showed a significant increase in flexural performance and an increase in stiffness compared to the unstrengthened RC beam. By increasing the elastic modulus, stiffness and the flexural strength of the strengthened beam increase. Namely, results of the FE model showed an increase of %59 in stiffness by strengthening RC beam with a 1 mm thick carbon TRM and a %63 increase by strengthening with a 1 mm thick PBO TRM.

The ductility is a major factor for any RC beam and especially has a main rule on seismic properties of RC beams. A ductile RC beam can take a large amount of strain while still resisting a sufficient amount of load. In other words, it is able to sustain large inelastic deformations before collapsing. The strengthened beams are less ductile than unstrengthened ones. Figure 10 shows decrease in ductility by increasing the elastic modulus.

Figure 11 shows that the steel yield point can change by adding reinforcing material (TRM); the

steel yield point will occur at a lower midpoint displacement. By adding more TRM plies or using another TRM with a higher modulus of elasticity, the steel yield point will occur even at lower midpoint displacements.

In the case that RC beam is reinforced with 1mm carbon or PBO textile, load-midpoint deflection curve shows a high stiffness and a very low ductility and has no clear steel yield point. It means by increasing the TRM reinforcement, the reinforced RC beam reaches to the concrete-controlled or compression failure mode. In this failure mode and before the steel reaches to the yield point, the concrete reaches to the maximum compressive strain and the concrete failure happens.

In contrast, in the case of reinforcing RC beam with a 1 mm thick steel textile, the steel yield point still exists and can be clearly identified. The steel yield point is achieved at the mid-point displacement of 8.20 mm and the load of 226.64 kN (Figure 11). In the case of the unstrengthened RC beam, the steel yield occurred at 9.35 mm mid-point displacement and 129.98 kN load.

5 Summary and Conclusions

The numerical results in this case study indicated that the TRM can be effectively used to rehabilitate or strengthen the RC beams.

For all types of textiles considered in the study, a notable increase in the flexural strength and a decrease in the midpoint displacement of the beams were achieved as compared to the original unstrengthened RC beam. The increase in the flexural strength and load carrying capacity of beam depends on reinforcement material, specifically its elastic modulus. Using the TRM with higher modulus of elasticity can increase the load carrying capacity of RC beam by an average of %63.

The other type of improvement in the performance of TRM reinforced RC beam was a decrease in bottom midpoint deflection by increasing the elastic modulus. Using the TRM with a higher modulus of elasticity increases the load carrying capacity of RC beam by the average of %63.

The other type of improvement in the performance of TRM reinforced RC beam was a decrease in bottom midpoint deflection and

enhancing the serviceability of the beam by increasing the TRM elastic modulus. This enhancement was 32% on average. It was also observed that in enhancing the load carrying capacity and serviceability there is an asymptotic limit.

The effect of TRM on load-deflection curve showed an increase in stiffness by average of %61 by increasing the textile elastic modulus. It also showed a notable influence on ductility and the steel yield. In particular, there was no clear steel yield point on the load-deflection curve when reinforcing with a 1 mm thick carbon or PBO TRC.

Fig. 1: TRM; the fibres are formed into the shape of a woven fabric (biaxial textile) reinforcement [10]

Fig. 2: TRM, the fibres are formed into a 3D textile reinforcement [10]

Fig. 3: Four-point flexural bending set-up of the RC beam studied

Fig. 4: Plastic strain distribution in the unstrengthened RC beam at failure point

Fig. 5: Plastic strain distribution in the carbon reinforced RC beam at failure point

Fig. 6: Load transfer behaviour between matrix and textile [4]

Fig. 7: The FE model results vs. experimental data and the analytical solution for the unstrengthened RC beam

Fig. 8: Load-deflection for beams strengthened with different textiles

Fig. 9: Normalized load vs. textile elastic modulus

Fig. 10: Normalized deflection vs. textile elastic modulus

Fig. 11: Effect of strengthening TRM on steel yield point of the RC beam

Table 1: The mechanical properties of concrete and steel rebar of the RC beam

	Concrete	Steel rebar
Elastic modulus (GPa)	30	200
Poisson's Ratio	0.2	0.3
Compression stress (MPa)	47.68	
Max compression strain	0.0035	
Yield stress (MPa)		523
Concrete beam size (L, b & h) (mm)	2200,400 & 250	
Rebar size		3-14

Table 2: Mechanical properties and thickness of the selected textile materials

	PBO fabric	Carbon fabric	Steel Fabric
Elastic modulus (GPa)	271	238	200
Poisson's Ratio	0.2	0.2	0.3
Nominal thickness(mm)	1	1	1

Table 3: Theoretical analysis of concrete beam

	Midpoint Deflection(mm)	Load (kN)
First crack point	0.91	38.36
Steel yield point	9.39	136.84
Ultimate load point	27.71	142.91

Table 4: Effect of TRM on mid-point displacement (serviceability)

Normalized mid-point displacement				
Rebar Size	TRM thickness (mm)*	Elastic Modulus		
		Steel	Carbon	PBO
3-12	0.05	1	0.947	0.928
3-12	0.15	1	0.766	0.632
3-12	0.25	1	0.540	0.519
3-14	0.05	1	0.865	0.803
3-14	0.15	1	0.646	0.541
3-14	0.25	1	0.515	0.495
3-16	0.05	1	0.874	0.864
3-16	0.15	1	0.824	0.792
3-16	0.25	1	0.809	0.774

* Nominal thickness

Table 5: Effect of TRM on load-carrying capacity

Normalized load-carrying capacity				
Rebar Size	TRM thickness (mm)*	Elastic Modulus		
		Steel	Carbon	PBO
3-12	0.05	1	1.436	1.486
3-12	0.15	1	1.630	1.643
3-12	0.25	1	1.669	1.723
3-14	0.05	1	1.271	1.290
3-14	0.15	1	1.392	1.442
3-14	0.25	1	1.475	1.536
3-16	0.05	1	1.177	1.224
3-16	0.15	1	1.249	1.273
3-16	0.25	1	1.339	1.365

* Nominal thickness

References

- [1] Nan Wang, Shi-lang Xu, "Flexural response of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with post-poured ultra high toughness cementitious composites layer", *Journal of Central South University of Technology*, Volume 18, Issue 3, pp 932-939, June 2011.
- [2] Chhabra Y., "Enhancing durability and sustainability of concrete structures", *36th Our World in Concrete and Structures (OWICs)*, 2011
- [3] D'Ambrisi A., Focacci F., "Flexural Strengthening of RC Beams with Textile Reinforcement Cement-Based Composites", *Journal of Composites for Construction*, ASCE, Page 707-720, September/October 2011.
- [4] Kaliakin V., Chajes M., T. F. Januszka, "Analysis of Concrete Beams Reinforced with Externally Bonded Woven Composite", *Composites Part B*, Volume 27, Issues 3-4, 1996.
- [5] Garden N. H., Quantrill R. J., Hollaway L. C., Thorne A. M., Parke G. A. R. , "An experimental study of the anchorage length of carbon fibre composite plates used to strengthen reinforced concrete beams", *Construction and Building Materials*, Volume 12, no. 4, pp. 203-219, 1998
- [6] Emadi J., Hashemi S. H., "Flexural study of high strength RC beams strengthened with CFRP plates", *World academy of Science*,

- Engineering and Technology* 54, page 380-384, 2011
- [7] Triantafillou T.C., Papanicolaou C.G., “Textile Reinforced Mortars (TRM) versus Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP) as Strengthening Materials of Concrete Structures”, *7th International Symposium on Fiber-Reinforced (FRP) Polymer Reinforcement for Concrete Structures*, American Concrete Institute 2005, page 99-118
- [8] Lepenies I., Meyer C., Schorn H., Zastrau B., “Modeling of Load Transfer Behavior of AR-Glass-Rovings in Textile Reinforced Concrete”, *ACI Journal*, Volume 244, 2008.
- [9] Antons U., Raupach M., Kulas C., Hegger J., “High-temperature tests on concrete specimens reinforced with alkali-resistant glass rovings under bending Loads”, *6th International Conference on FRP Composites in Civil Engineering (CICE) 2012*, Rome, Italy, 13-15 June 2012
- [10] Katz A., Tsesarsky M., Peled A., Anteby I., “Textile Reinforced Cementitious Composites for Retrofit and Strengthening of Concrete Structures under Impact Loading”, *High Performance Fiber Reinforced Cement Composites 6*, pp 503-510, 2012
- [11] Dai J.G., Wang B., Xu S.L., “Textile Reinforced Engineered Cementitious Composites (TR-ECC) Overlays for the strengthening of RC Beams”, *The second official international conference of International Institute for FRP in Construction for Asia-Pacific Region*, pages 75-80, 2009
- [12] Lepenies I. G., Richter M., Zastrau B. W., “A multi-scale analysis of textile reinforced concrete structures”. *79th Annual Meeting of the International Association of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics (GAMM)*, Bremen 2008, Volume 8, Issue 1, pages 10553–10554, December 2008.
- [13] Garcia D., Alonso P., San-Jose J.T., Garmendia L., Perlot C., “Confinement of medium strength concrete cylinders with ballast TRM” *13th International congress on polymers in concrete*, 2010
- [14] Bournas D.A., Triantafillou T.C., “Flexural strengthening of RC columns with Nee surface Mounted FRP or stainless steel reinforcement: experimental investigation”, *The 14th world conference on earthquake engineering*, Oct 12-17, 2008, Beijing, China
- [15] Bournas D.A., Triantafillou T.C., “Innovative seismic retrofitting of old-type RC columns through jacketing: Textile-reinforced mortars (TRM) versus fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP)”, *The 14th world conference on earthquake engineering*, Oct 12-17, 2008, Beijing, China
- [16] Vasconcelos G., Figueiro R., Cunha F., Abreu S., “Retrofitting masonry infill walls with textile reinforced mortar (TRM)”, *15th world Conference on earthquake engineering*, Lisbon, Portugal, 24-28 September 2012